

Learning from Long-Term Care practices
for the European Care Strategy

NATIONAL REPORT DENMARK: THE MEANINGS OF INEQUALITIES IN LTC IN DENMARK

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Contents

The meanings of Inequalities in LTC in Denmark	4
Brief summary.....	4
1. Definitions.....	4
2. Boundaries, Differentiation, Interrelations.....	6
3. Resources, Infrastructure, Regulation	6
4. Stakeholders, Governance.....	9
5. Debates, Strategies	10
Literature	11

The meanings of Inequalities in LTC in Denmark

Brief summary

The focus in the following is related to the understanding of inequalities regarding Long-Term Care in Denmark. Formally, there is equality in access and all legally residing in Denmark have access to LTC if they fulfil the criteria. Whether all gets the same service is an open question due to different implementations and priorities across municipalities. The focus is on the role of the public sector.

1. Definitions

In principle, all who have a need is covered by the legislation and the interpretation hereof is that citizens with the same need shall have the same service, conditioned on the context such as whether the citizen is living with a partner or not. Therefore, there is in no official document definitions of this, and this is also the case for the legislation. There might albeit be variations due to the right of local municipalities to vary the level of service they deliver in accordance with the resources they have available and local political preferences. So, at the local level the services shall in principle be the same for all within a municipality under the condition that the needs assessment is the same for all similar same cases, whereas at the same time it can vary across municipalities. There is no means-test for receiving long-term care and personal care and cleaning is free of charge, whereas living in a home for elderly people there is a payment reflecting the cost hereof, albeit so that the cost will not imply that a person will not be able to pay and still have some money left. Thus, the cost is not an issue when it comes to inequality in the access of long-term care. If one considers health (such as medicine and dental care) then there might be inequalities due to user charges, especially for medicine.

There is no indication in Denmark of non-take up of services, which could be one element of inequality. This also due to the fact that there are preventable home visits (people can say no).

The access to informal care can have an impact on the support the elderly receive. A limited qualitative study of informal care to elderly living in their own home argued that there is very limited knowledge in Denmark concerning informal care, including intensive informal care. A number of elderly receives help from others to a number of issues (such as home, pc, driving), albeit the number

of hours and who is doing it is not clear. The concept of informal care is often used very broadly and is often not defined in the studies. Studies mainly look into family carers, however not friends or others helping the elderly (Andersen, Hjorth-Enemark, and Spare 2023). They further argue that international studies cannot be transferred to a Danish context, among other things due to high labour market participation and that elderly in Denmark prefer to be cared for by professionals.

One element in the quality of care has been argued to be the users' ability to make choices, such as choosing between different providers of care.

However, as an article shows that a voucher market, which could be one way to provide users with choice, might without price competition production cost will be increased with regard to practical help as this is what was studied (Foged and Houlberg 2023). There might further be regional differences given that the possibility of making a choice might vary across areas with many or few providers. This is also due to the fact that the economies of scale of public production might be reduced. Thus, a possible inequality arises from the circumstances that some have fewer choices than others, and also at the same time that choice in itself might prove and imply inequality in who is and who is not able to make a rational informed decision. This was mentioned by several stakeholders in the conducted interviews: There is a risk of geographical inequality between municipalities in terms of whether they can have the same level of services, especially in some of the more remote areas of the country. But there is also a potential social bias, where those who are more resourceful are better at articulating their needs and thus may receive more help, all else being equal, than those who have greater needs but are less able to articulate their needs. So, we must also be very aware of this social bias.

Inequalities are not a central policy issue within long-term care with the exception of the discussion relating to the fact that some are able to buy supplementary services whereas others are not and are thus also framed in the debates about the degree of economic inequality. There is therefore also only limited data, and they might not really be comparable as well as they do not inform about possible inequalities in the Danish system. For data on staff one might, for example, use OECD data Perhaps best if for comparison to use: [https://data-explorer.oecd.org/?fs\[0\]=Topic%2C1%7CHealth%23HEA%23%7CLong-term%20care%23HEA_LTC%23&pg=0&fc=Topic&bp=true&snb=4](https://data-explorer.oecd.org/?fs[0]=Topic%2C1%7CHealth%23HEA%23%7CLong-term%20care%23HEA_LTC%23&pg=0&fc=Topic&bp=true&snb=4), OECD Data Explorer, accessed the 16th January, 2025.

2. Boundaries, Differentiation, Interrelations

Overall focus is on inequalities regarding delivery of LTC to those eligible for the services.

This is also witnessed by that at the outset there is no monitoring of inequalities in LTC as this with the universalistic approach, with the caveats mentioned above, is expected not to be the case.

There is an option for citizens to appeal a municipal decision on the level of services to a National Appeal Board that is also an instrument to ensure that equal cases are equally treated.

The National Board of Appeal¹ has clarified in an appeal case that support from the Law on Social Service builds upon the fact that the individual has a responsibility for own and family, and that practical support shall be given to tasks that the citizens are not able to do themselves. If one is not able to do the task, they will first have to try rehabilitation before embarking upon support. Even when municipalities have to write quality standards, they are not obliged to offer support if the citizens might be able to do the task themselves. Thus, if a person is able to use a PC to buy daily necessities online the municipality is not obliged to support with this and nor to pay for the cost of transport of the goods. In recent years also the use of robot vacuum cleaners has been so ordinary within the Danish society that some municipalities ask elderly to buy these themselves.

Inequalities related to variations in the elderly's abilities to buy extra services are only more limited an issue, see albeit Foged and Houlberg, 2023.

3. Resources, Infrastructure, Regulation

Overall, there is only very limited data that might give indications of that there is inequality in LTC, including whether judgement of needs varies among those responsible for deciding whether or not a person is having the right to receive home care. People have the right to access a home for elderly

¹ [Forsiden — Ankestyrelsen \(ast.dk\)](#), is where citizens can complain about a municipality's decision on the level of service according the judgement of the need of the individual.

people if deemed necessary and can choose among homes in all of Denmark. If they have a specific home in mind they might have to wait a little while. So, there is in principle no inequality in access to institutional long-term care if in need of a place.

In Figure 1 the variation in number of persons deemed eligible for home help services in 2023 across municipalities is indicated by the percentage above the age of 65 who receives home care by the different municipalities.

Andel af befolkningen i alderen 65+ år visiteret til hjemmehjælp i eget hjem fordelt efter kommune. 2023

Anm.: Lyngby-Taarbæk Kommune har ikke godkendt data for dele af perioden og indgår således ikke i figuren. Befolkningen er opgjort pr. 1. januar 2024.

Source: [NYT: 156.800 personer visiteret til hjemmehjælp i 2023 - Danmarks Statistik \(dst.dk\)](#).

Note: The headline says in English: Percentage of citizens aged 65+ in 2023 receiving care in own home distributed across municipalities. For Lyngby-Tårnbæk municipality there is no data.

As can be witnessed from Figure 1 there is a strong variation with the percentage receiving home care being double as high in some municipalities than in other municipalities. It is possible to get some information on different types of care in homes. Part of the difference between municipalities witness variations in the socioeconomic situation, part of which can be variations in local priorities as there is no common national definition of what need is. Difference in age structure might also influence the percentage given that there is a connection between age and use and support for home care, and it is possible to find data on age and support which confirms an age gradient. Thus, even if the data in Figure 1 at the outset shows variations and thereby inequalities this cannot be concluded based upon this information. Albeit the data indicates that there is inequality in access to home care between municipalities, but the size hereof is not possible to estimate as one then would need to have access to information on, for example, the health of the individual deemed eligible to receive care.

In principle, there can also be inequalities due to differences in the take-up rate of services, albeit there is no data to indicate whether or not this is the case. Given there are preventative visits, and in general, no indication of lack of take-up this is not considered to be an issue.

Furthermore, as the support of a partner can have an impact on the access to some practical home services, this might imply that two persons with the same need gets different support. This also, albeit implicitly, implies that women often do more informal care than men due to the typical differences in age for couples living together with the men on average having a higher age than women.

Another possible type of inequality relates to that municipalities have to ensure a free-choice between different providers, e.g. a public and recognised private providers, albeit the prices to be paid by the municipality to the private providers are fixed on level with the cost the municipality spend when they provide the service. Still, it is not obvious that all citizens are able to make a choice to the same degree. Choice is at the same time more difficult for some than for others, and thereby this might create inequalities (Greve 2011; Jordahl and Persson 2021; Bergman, Jordahl, and Lundberg 2018).

For those wanting more services than provided by the public sector there can be an issue regarding the ability to pay private providers for extra services, which then might increase inequality in the access to the same level of LTC as this will be influenced by the inequality in income. This mainly, however, refers to the issue of practical support in private homes.

4. Stakeholders, Governance

It is the same actors involved as with regard to the other concepts, e.g. municipalities, employees and users within an overall national framework set by the state and with degrees of freedom for the municipalities within this overall framework.

We have conducted 15 interviews with different stakeholders within long-term care in Denmark, and all but 3 of the interviewees stated that there is inequality and/or differences from municipality to municipality in the Danish long-term care. Only 2 of the interviewees mentioned it without first being asked about it. The interviews show thereby that inequality is not at first hand considered one of the major problems in the Danish long-term care. The reason for inequalities is as mentioned earlier that: "There is municipal self-government, and the responsibility lies with the municipalities, so fundamentally, it cannot be the same everywhere. You have different service levels, use different funds, and resources from one municipality to another, so there are also significant differences in terms of the resources allocated to the area. So, there are differences." This in combination with that "There are geographical and economic differences in the municipalities' conditions for providing uniform assistance."

The stakeholders who mentioned inequality without being asked, mentioned it in relation to the possibilities of buying extra help as a cause of inequality, and another stakeholder mentioned the differences in the municipalities' service as a big challenge: " There is a very, very big difference, and in reality, it is also a challenge we have, that there is actually a big difference in what you get depending on where you live in the country."

At the same time a stakeholder stated that: "Everyone can receive the same care and help at some level in the municipalities. However, municipalities have different service standards, so in that way, there can be some differences. But it is not a matter of health inequality or social inequality".

One of the main issues is that the ability to buy supplementary services might vary, but also as shown in the previous section that there can be variations in how a proportion of elderly get support. However, a problem is that a variation in the number of elderly getting support among municipalities might be due to differences in socioeconomic conditions and can therefore not directly be used as an argument for inequality.

5. Debates, Strategies

The issue of inequality is not a strong issue in the Danish debate related to long-term care. The debates relate more to whether the public support is sufficient and if not whether this implies that those who can afford to pay for more services get this whereas others do not. This in connection with the debate on whether citizens can buy supplementary services from the provider of the paid public services with own payment.

The variation in the level of service among municipalities is also discussed, however at the same time there is an issue about the municipalities' right to make decisions based upon local political priorities, and variations in the socioeconomic composition of the citizens.

Even though the issue of inequality is not a strong issue in the Danish public debate several of the stakeholders in our interviews mentioned that inequality is at stake in the Danish long-term care. This was especially in relation to the variations in the municipalities, as a stakeholder stated when asked if there is equal access to care: "There is municipal self-government, and the responsibility lies with the municipalities, so fundamentally, it cannot be the same everywhere. You have different service levels, use different funds, and resources from one municipality to another, so there are also significant differences in terms of the resources allocated to the area. So, there are differences."

An issue is that if the citizens shall have a stronger influence on what more specific type of services they get in the future, then this opens the dilemma that some will be better able to argue for what they need than others, albeit the total time of services to the individual person in need will most likely not be increased

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